

Analysis of students' perceptions of the school climate: comparative case study of 2 schools in Morocco

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ABSTRACT:

The effect of school climate (SC) on teaching, learning, and academic achievement is a topic studied by many researchers (Debarbieux, 2015); (Collins, T. N., 2010); (Thapa et al., 2013). Some researchers have studied the problem from the perspective of the conditions for improving SC (Veltcheff, 2015); (Elhaddadi, 2019); (Ramdé, 2011); (Poulin et al., 2018). Nevertheless, while evaluating SC, few studies focus on students, who are indeed at the heart of the educational process. Therefore, our study is particularly interested in the evaluation of SC by analyzing students' perceptions in 2 public primary schools in Morocco. To collect data, we carried out semi-structured focus group interviews and a multi-criteria scoring. Subsequently, a qualitative analysis of the responses and the creation of a SC index from the analysis of the multi-criteria evaluation data were conducted by school and then comparatively. The study allowed the disclosure of the determinants that influence students' perceptions of SC, namely the state of infrastructure, distance to school, the degree of parents' involvement, and relations with the school community.¹

Keywords: Determinant; evaluation; involvement; teachers; well-being

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